

Rice blast (B1) pathogen *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav. in Tamil Nadu, India

V. Mariappan, associate professor of Plant Pathology, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 3, India

B1 was a major problem in Tamil Nadu until resistant rice varieties were introduced in the 1960s. Even B1 incidence in susceptible varieties was low until 1980. Since 1980, B1 incidence has increased for all varieties and has become a serious constraint to rice production.

P. oryzae, the causal fungus, was isolated from the infected leaves and inoculated on the international differentials and other varieties to assess their reaction (see table). The isolate of *P. oryzae* did not infect Raminad Str. 3, NP125, Usen, and Dular, which are indicators of the IA, IC, ID, and IE international race groups. Earlier reports had indicated that the *P. oryzae* isolates in Tamil Nadu belong to the race groups IA, IC, ID, and IF, which infect Raminad Str. 3, NP125, Usen, and Kanto 51.

Our observations indicate some changes in the pathogen population, based on the susceptible reaction of Dular and the other varieties which were considered field resistant. □

Reaction of international differentials or varieties to the *P. oryzae* isolate of Tamil Nadu, India. ^a

Differential cultivars and varieties	Indicator	Type of reaction
Raminad	IA	Lesions, B type
Zenith	IB	No reaction
NP125	IC	Lesions, D type
Usen	ID	Lesions, C type
Dular	IE	Lesions, D type
Kanto 51	IF	No reaction
CI 8970	IG	Not tested
Caloro	IH	No reaction
CI 5309		Flecks, A type
Fukunishiki		Lesions, D type
Aichi-Asahi		No reaction
Ishikari Shiroke		Lesions, C type
Chokoto		No reaction
Tsuyuake		No reaction
Taichung (TCWC)		Flecks, A type
Wagwag		Lesions, C type
Sha-tiao-tsao		No reaction
Khao-tah-haeng 17		Flecks, A type
CI 8985 Lacrosse		No reaction
Peta		No reaction
Pai-kan-tao		No reaction
Pi No. 4		No reaction
Yashiromochi		No reaction
Co 25 (xx)		Flecks, A type
Kataktara D42		Lesions, D type
CI 5309		Lesions, D type
IR50		Lesions, D type
Annapoorna		Flecks, A type
Akashi		Lesions, C type
Rasi (x)		No reaction
Co 41		Lesions, B type
Co 39		Lesions, B type
IR36		No reaction
IR28		No reaction

Co 29	No reaction
ADT31	No reaction
Ponmani (x)	Lesions, B type
TKM9	Lesions, D type
Co 43 (x)	No reaction
PY 1	Flecks, A type
MDU 1	Lesions, B type
Bhavani	No reaction
ASD15	Lesions, D type
Co 44	Lesions, C type
ADT36 (x)	Lesions, B type
ADT35 (x)	Lesions, B type
Co 42	Lesions, B type
TKM6	No reaction
Co 36	Lesions, D type
IR20	Flecks, A type
IR22	Lesions, B type
IR34	No reaction
IR54	No reaction
Jaya	Lesions, D type
Paiyur 1	Lesions, B type
Ponni	Lesions, B type
ACK 1	Lesions, D type
ACM 2	Lesions, C type
ACM 3	No reaction
TI 1334	No reaction
AS688	No reaction
AC19789	Lesions, B type
TP1974	No reaction
Py 2	No reaction
Vaigai (x)	Lesions, B type
Pennai	Lesions, D type
Kaveri	Lesions, D type
Co 33	Lesions, B type
Kannagi	Lesions, D type
Kanchi	Lesions, B type

^a A = flecks, B = reddish brown spot, C circular spots (1 mm) with a central white speck, D = spindle lesions (2 mm). (x) = field resistant, (xx) = resistant.

Methods and timing of fungicide application to control rice blast (B1) under favorable upland conditions in Colombia

S. W. Ahn and M. Rubiano, Rice Program, Centro Internacional de Agricultura Tropical, Colombia

Timing of foliar fungicide application to control B1 is based mainly on growth stage or a chronological schedule. However, timing can be flexible if it is based on actual disease development at a given growth stage as influenced by weather, particularly rain in the tropics.

Under favorable upland conditions in Colombia, most of the foliar fungicide applications can be replaced with seed treatment. Furthermore, field observations indicate that additional application

Effects of method and timing of fungicide application on B1 severity and yield of CICA4, Santa Rosa, Villavicencio, Colombia. ^a

Applications (no.)	Treatment ^b		B1 severity (%)		Yield (t/ha)
	For leaf B1	For panicle B1	Leaf	Panicle	
3-4	1. Seed treatment 2. Foliar application for more than 5% infection before maximum tillering	3. Booting stage 4. 50% panicle emergence	9.7 b	3.3 b	4.1 a
4	1. Initial symptom 2. Maximum tillering	3. Booting stage 4. 50% panicle emergence	14.3 b 3.7 c	5.7 b 2 b	4 a 4.2 a
6	1. 30 d after sowing (DAS) 2. 40 DAS 3. 50 DAS 4. 60 DAS	5. 80 DAS 6. 60% panicle emergence			
0	No chemical application		51 a	40.7 a	2.4 b

^a Means of 3 experiments, 3 replications/experiment. In a column, values with common letters are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^b Foliar application (300 g ai/ha) and seed treatment (1.1 g ai/kg of seeds) were made with tricyclazole (WP 75%).

is needed only if severity exceeds 5% diseased leaf area before maximum tillering, in the case of highly susceptible cultivars. This concept was tested under favorable upland conditions using CICA4, a highly susceptible cultivar in Colombia. The experiment was repeated three times

at different periods.

Results showed that one application can be eliminated without serious damage or yield loss to rice (see table). Additional application was required only once.

Results from other experiments showed that application at 50% panicle emergence

of moderately BI-resistant cultivars could be eliminated if the average daily precipitation 10-15 d after flowering is less than 2 or more than 18 mm. Disease severity data indicated that the optimum average daily precipitation during this critical period is about 10 mm. □

Relationship between susceptibility to leaf blast (BI) and panicle BI severity

S. W. Ahn and M. Rubiano, Rice Program, Centro Internacional de Agricultura Tropical, Colombia

Differences in leaf BI and panicle BI susceptibility in the field may be caused by varying macro- or microclimate conditions during disease development. We studied 15 cultivars with different reactions to leaf and panicle BI at Villavicencio.

Plantings were staggered to synchronize the evaluation of leaf and panicle BI and to eliminate the effect of different weather on BI development. Planting density was higher than normal (200 kg seed/ha) to provide a favorable microclimate for leaf BI development.

There was a highly positive relationship between leaf BI infection level and panicle BI severity (see figure), which shows that cultivars genetically susceptible to a population of certain BI races are susceptible to both leaf and panicle infection.

The frequently observed difference

between leaf and panicle BI reaction in the field may be due to the changes in micro- or macroclimates during distinct growth phases. Generally, the microclimate influence is greater on leaf BI

development than on panicle BI. Changes in the frequency of races in the population of *Pyricularia oryzae* in a crop season could also influence leaf and panicle reaction. □

Relationship between panicle and leaf BI severity. Evaluations were made at the same time and place in synchronized plantings. DAS = days after sowing.

Influence of planting time on blast (BI) incidence

S. Mohan, research associate; P. Vasudevan, associate professor; and B. Gururajan, associate professor, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University Research Centre, Vellore 632001, India

Environmental factors influence the epidemiology of BI caused by *Pyricularia oryzae*. We studied the influence of environment on BI incidence on IR50, which was recently introduced in North Arcot. IR50 matures early (105 to 110 d) and has high yield potential.

IR50 was transplanted on different dates in 1983 rabi. Total leaves and leaves with spindle-shaped BI spots were counted from 50 randomly selected hills/field at tillering and percent BI incidence was calculated (see table). Minimum and maximum temperatures and relative humidity (RH) were recorded when fields were scored.

Highest BI incidence was in the crop planted in mid-Dec, followed by that planted in early Jan (see table). BI incidence was lowest in the earliest sown crop perhaps because the temperature was higher and RH lower than with the crops sown later. □

Effect of planting time on BI incidence, Vellore, India.

Planting date	Diseased leaves (%)	Max temp (°C)	Min temp (°C)	Relative humidity (%)
25 Oct	3	32.2	22.8	87
18 Nov	51	30.6	20.1	84
5 Dec	62	26.9	19.6	96
17 Dec	85	26.9	19.6	96
3 Jan	71	29.1	17.9	92